

Study of Platelet Indices in Pregnancy-Induced Hypertension (PIH)Emmanuel Anugrah Soreng¹, Vibhuti Bhushan Kumar Choudhary², Shweta Sahay³,
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Abstract:**Background:** Pregnancy-induced hypertension (PIH) is a major global cause of morbidity and mortality among mothers and newborns. Because of their link to endothelial dysfunction and platelet activation, platelet indices such as platelet count, mean platelet volume (MPV), platelet distribution width (PDW), and plateletcrit (PCT) have been suggested as possible biomarkers for the early detection and management of PIH.**Aim:** This study aims to investigate the relationship between platelet indices and PIH in pregnant women, evaluating their potential utility as diagnostic and prognostic markers for PIH.**Methods:** 200 pregnant women were included in a cross-sectional observational study; 100 of them had been diagnosed with PIH, while the other 100 were normotensive controls. Standard laboratory procedures were used to quantify platelet indices and gather demographic and clinical data. In order to find significant predictors of PIH, statistical analysis was carried out using SPSS version 23.0, which included independent t-tests, Chi-square tests, and multivariate logistic regression.**Results:** The PIH group exhibited significantly lower platelet counts ($p < 0.001$) and higher MPV ($p < 0.001$) and PDW ($p < 0.001$) compared to the control group. Multivariate logistic regression identified lower platelet count (OR = 0.92, $p < 0.001$) and higher MPV (OR = 1.48, $p < 0.001$) as independent predictors of PIH. These findings suggest that altered platelet indices are closely associated with the pathophysiology of PIH.**Conclusion:** The study demonstrates that platelet indices, particularly platelet count and MPV, are significantly altered in women with PIH and can serve as valuable biomarkers for the early detection and management of the condition. Routine monitoring of these indices during pregnancy could enhance the early identification of women at risk for PIH, potentially improving maternal and fetal outcomes.**Recommendations:** It is suggested that more studies be conducted to confirm these results in bigger, more varied populations and to investigate the incorporation of platelet indices into common prenatal screening procedures for PIH.**Keywords:** Pregnancy-Induced Hypertension, Platelet Indices, Mean Platelet Volume, Biomarkers, Early Detection.

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Introduction

An important public health concern, (PIH) affects 5–10% of pregnancies worldwide. Especially in poor nations, it is among the leading causes of illness and death in pregnant women and young children. Preterm birth, intrauterine growth restriction, and placental abruption are just a few of the serious consequences that can result from preterm delivery and PIH, which is a spectrum of hypertensive disorders that includes gestational hypertension, preeclampsia, and eclampsia [1]. The exact cause of PIH is still unknown despite a great deal of research; however it is generally acknowledged that aberrant placentation and endothelial dysfunction are important factors [2].

The tiniest blood cells, called platelets, are essential for preserving vascular integrity and haemostasis. According to recent research, hypertensive disorders of pregnancy may affect platelet indices, such as platelet count, (PDW), (MPV), and plateletcrit (PCT), which may thus function as possible biomarkers for the early diagnosis of PIH [3]. Changes in these indicators are thought to be a reflection of elevated platelet consumption and activation, which are traits of the hypercoagulable state seen in PIH [4].

Because of increased platelet aggregation and consumption in response to endothelial damage, women with PIH often have decreased platelet counts [5]. The average platelet volume, or MPV,

is frequently higher in patients with peripheral ischaemic haemolysis (PIH), which may reflect the existence of larger, more reactive platelets that are discharged into circulation as a result of higher platelet turnover [6]. PDW, a metric that quantifies platelet size variability, is also observed to be higher in PIH, indicating the heterogeneity of platelet morphology [7].

Changes in PIH can also be seen in PCT, which is a measure of total platelet mass, albeit its clinical importance is not fully understood [8]. There is increasing interest in examining these platelet indices' capacity to forecast the development and severity of PIH due to their possible use in the early diagnosis and treatment of the illness. According to recent research, women with hypertension diseases who have changed platelet indices are more likely to experience unfavourable pregnancy outcomes. This suggests that normal prenatal screening techniques might include these markers. This study aims to investigate the relationship between platelet indices and PIH in pregnant women, evaluating their potential utility as diagnostic and prognostic markers for PIH.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a cross-sectional observational analysis.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at MGM Medical College, a tertiary care center located in Jamshedpur, Jharkhand. The hospital serves a large population and is well-equipped with facilities for the management of obstetric cases, including those with hypertensive disorders.

Participants: A total of 200 pregnant women were recruited for this study. The participants were divided into two groups: 100 women diagnosed with (PIH) and 100 normotensive pregnant women serving as the control group.

Inclusion Criteria:

- **Age and Gestation:** Pregnant women aged 18-40 years, with 24-40 weeks of gestation.
- **PIH Diagnosis:** Blood pressure $\geq$ 140/90 mmHg after 20 weeks of gestation.
- **Consent:** Women who provided informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria:

- **Pre-existing Conditions:** Excludes women with pre-existing hypertension, chronic conditions (e.g., diabetes, renal disease).
- **Multiple Pregnancies:** Excludes women with multiple pregnancies.
- **Bleeding Issues:** Excludes those with bleeding disorders or on anticoagulant therapy.

- **Thrombocytopenia:** Excludes women with a history of thrombocytopenia before pregnancy

Bias: To minimize bias, the study employed a strict inclusion and exclusion criteria, ensuring a homogenous population. Random sampling was used to select participants from those meeting the criteria. The investigators and laboratory personnel were blinded to the group allocation to prevent observer bias during data collection and analysis.

Data Collection: A combination of laboratory testing, medical record reviews, and patient interviews were used to gather data. Demographic information, obstetric history, and clinical data were recorded. Blood samples were collected from all participants under aseptic conditions for the analysis of platelet indices.

Procedure

1. **Recruitment and Consent:** Eligible participants were identified and recruited during their antenatal visits. Every participant gave their informed consent.
2. **Blood Sample Collection:** All participants had venous blood samples taken in accordance with a defined protocol. In order to measure platelet indices, such as platelet count, MPV, PDW, and PCT, samples were processed right away.
3. **Data Recording:** The gathered data, including platelet indices and clinical parameters, were recorded in a pre-designed case report form.

Statistical Analysis: The statistical analysis was carried out using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics summarised demographic and clinical characteristics. Platelet indices in the PIH and control groups were compared using independent t-tests or Mann-Whitney U tests, with Chi-square tests for categorical variables. P-values <0.05 were considered significant. Multivariate logistic regression revealed independent predictors of PIH, with results expressed as odds ratios (OR) and 95% confidence intervals.

Ethical Considerations: The study was authorised by the institutional ethics committee. All participants gave written informed consent and their confidentiality was maintained throughout the study. This methodology outlines a comprehensive approach to examining the relationship between platelet indices and PIH, ensuring robust data collection and analysis.

Results

A total of 200 pregnant women participated in the study, with 100 women diagnosed with (PIH) and 100 normotensive women serving as the control group. The mean age of the participants in the PIH group was 29.3 ± 4.5 years, compared to 28.7 ± 4.7

years in the control group, with no statistically significant difference ($p = 0.324$). The mean gestational age at the time of enrollment was $32.2 \pm$

3.6 weeks in the PIH group and 31.9 ± 3.8 weeks in the control group ($p = 0.567$).

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	PIH Group (n = 100)	Control Group (n = 100)	p-value
Age (years)	29.3 ± 4.5	28.7 ± 4.7	0.324
Gestational Age (weeks)	32.2 ± 3.6	31.9 ± 3.8	0.567
Nulliparous (%)	46	50	0.598
BMI (kg/m ²)	28.4 ± 3.2	27.9 ± 3.1	0.422
Systolic BP (mmHg)	145.8 ± 10.3	118.6 ± 8.7	<0.001*
Diastolic BP (mmHg)	94.6 ± 6.8	75.4 ± 6.5	<0.001*

The mean platelet count in the PIH group was significantly lower compared to the control group ($186.2 \pm 45.3 \times 10^9/L$ vs. $237.4 \pm 50.2 \times 10^9/L$, $p < 0.001$). The mean platelet volume (MPV) was significantly higher in the PIH group (11.1 ± 1.3 fL) compared to the control group (9.9 ± 1.2 fL, $p < 0.001$). (PDW) and (PCT) were also significantly different between the two groups.

Table 2: Comparison of Platelet Indices between PIH and Control Groups

Platelet Index	PIH Group (n = 100)	Control Group (n = 100)	p-value
Platelet Count ($\times 10^9/L$)	186.2 ± 45.3	237.4 ± 50.2	<0.001*
MPV (fL)	11.1 ± 1.3	9.9 ± 1.2	<0.001*
(PDW)	15.7 ± 2.1	14.2 ± 1.8	<0.001*
Plateletcrit (PCT, %)	0.21 ± 0.05	0.24 ± 0.04	0.002*

A multivariate logistic regression analysis was conducted to identify independent predictors of PIH. The analysis showed that lower platelet count (OR = 0.92, 95% CI: 0.89–0.95, $p < 0.001$), higher MPV (OR = 1.48, 95% CI: 1.21–1.81, $p < 0.001$), and higher PDW (OR = 1.35, 95% CI: 1.12–1.63, $p = 0.002$) were significant independent predictors of PIH.

Table 3: Multivariate Logistic Regression Analysis for Predictors of PIH

Variable	OR	95% CI	p-value
Platelet Count ($\times 10^9/L$)	0.92	0.89 – 0.95	<0.001*
(MPV)	1.48	1.21 – 1.81	<0.001*
(PDW)	1.35	1.12 – 1.63	0.002*
Gestational Age (weeks)	1.05	0.98 – 1.13	0.154
BMI (kg/m ²)	1.04	0.96 – 1.12	0.312

Discussion

The results revealed significant differences in platelet indices between the two groups, suggesting that these hematological markers could be valuable in the early detection and management of PIH. The PIH group exhibited a significantly lower mean platelet count compared to the control group, indicating a possible association between PIH and platelet consumption or destruction. Additionally, the PDW and MPV were significantly higher in the PIH group, reflecting larger and more heterogeneous platelets. These findings suggest increased platelet activation and turnover in women with PIH, which could contribute to the pathophysiology of the condition.

The multivariate logistic regression analysis further supported the importance of platelet indices in PIH. Lower platelet count and higher MPV emerged as significant independent predictors of PIH, highlighting their potential role in identifying women at risk for developing this hypertensive disorder. These results suggest that routine monitoring of platelet indices during pregnancy, particularly in those with risk factors for

hypertension, could provide valuable insights for early diagnosis and intervention.

Manchanda and Malik (2020) discovered that patients with PIH had considerably higher platelet indices than normotensive pregnant women, including (MPV), (PDW), and (P-LCR). According to the study, these raised platelet indices have a strong correlation with the intensity of hypertensive crises in patients with PIH, which makes them useful indicators for forecasting unfavourable outcomes in pregnancies affected by the condition [10].

These results were further supported by a 2022 study which showed that when PIH severity grows, MPV tends to rise while platelet count tends to fall. The results of the study showed that these indices, in particular the ratio of MPV to platelet count, are very sensitive and specific in identifying pre-eclampsia in the absence of severe symptoms. This emphasises how helpful these markers are in clinical practice as prognostic tools [11].

In a more recent 2023 study, it was discovered that, in comparison to normotensive controls, PIH

patients had significantly lower platelet counts as well as higher MPV and PDW levels in a rural Western Indian tertiary care context. According to the study's findings, these platelet indices are useful for determining the severity of PIH early on and at a reasonable cost. This discovery holds special significance in environments with low resources, when access to sophisticated diagnostic instruments may be restricted [12].

Conclusion

The study underscores the clinical importance of platelet indicators in the setting of PIH.

The findings suggest that alterations in platelet count, MPV, and PDW could serve as early indicators of PIH, offering healthcare providers additional tools for the timely identification and management of this condition. Further research is needed to investigate the underlying mechanisms linking platelet indices to PIH and to establish standardized guidelines for their use in clinical practice.

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